

LEADERSHIP STRATEGIES ON PERFORMANCE IN COUNTY GOVERNMENT OF UASIN GISHU, KENYA

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of leadership strategies on performance of Uasin Gishu County. The study was guided by the following specific objectives; to evaluate the effect of work environment on performance in Uasin Gishu County. The study was guided by Transformational Leadership Theory. A descriptive survey research design was employed with a target population of 95 respondents consisting of the county executive committee members, county chief officers, county directors, chief principals, and principals. The data collection instrument was questionnaires both closed and open ended. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. Data collected using questionnaires was entered and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software. In addition, inferential statistics that include Analysis of variance, Pearson correlation and multiple regression analysis was used establishing the nature and extent of relationship between variables. To ascertain the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable, a regression model was used. In conclusion basing on the findings, the study concluded that working environment has a significant effect on performance of Uasin Gishu county government. The study recommended that the management of the county government of Uasin Gishu should provide their employees a fair and conducive working condition to enable high performance. Due to an ever changing environment, the county government of Uasin Gishu should embrace regular trainings to enhance high and required competencies that facilitates good county government performance. The management of the county government of Uasin Gishu should establish a good relationship with their stakeholders through provision of good reception to enhance customer satisfaction. The study is useful to all the stakeholders in the County governments.

Keywords: Working Environment, Organizational Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The core purpose of leadership strategic theory and research is to understand how much influence top executives have over performance (Singh et al. 2016). Empirical and conceptual studies have shown that strategic leadership actions significantly influence performance (Quigley & Graffin, 2017; unfortunately, other studies conclude that their actions are impeded by situational constraints, inertia or random effects, such that they don't have much leeway over performance (Fitza, 2017; Haveman, 1992). These divergent findings indicate either a lack of evidence in establishing a direct

association between strategic leadership and performance or of the many confounding variables that make it difficult to demonstrate a clear cause and effect (Knies et al., 2016). Hambrick & Quigley (2014) point out that scholars are yet to agree on the conceptualization and operationalization of contextual conditions strategic leaders face. A leadership strategy makes explicit how many leaders we need, of what kind, where, with what skills, and behaving in what fashion individually and collectively to achieve the total success we seek. A good leadership strategy takes all necessary factors into account. Simply having all of the leadership positions on the organization chart filled will not produce the leadership that is required to implement strategies, adapt to change, support innovation or other important organizational agendas. It is not just having the right number of bodies, it is what those bodies do and how they relate to one another that matters.

Leadership strategies are based on a thorough analysis of the current situation and an informed view of the future. The strategy then provides a series of recommendations to close the gap between the current situation and desired future. Once the leadership strategy is known, a leadership development strategy can be formulated to produce the desired future state, and implications for talent management processes can be identified. When the strategy is implemented, business results will provide feedback on how well the leadership strategy is working and help shape what new business strategies can be considered with the leadership talent that has been developed. In reality, the leadership strategy implications would be much more specific, reflecting the actual opportunities and issues surrounding the key drivers. The key drivers and their associated business strategies should have clear implications for what leaders must do well in order for the organization to succeed. Ultimately, leadership development activities should be designed to ensure that individual leaders and the collective leadership of the organization are prepared to implement the most important strategies related to the key drivers.

The leadership strategies may also include specific target dates for each action, who is responsible, barriers to success, costs and implications for leadership development or talent management processes. Various scholars have argued that methodological and statistical limitations, unavailability of relevant control variables and contexts have systematically undermined the effect of strategic leadership on performance (Fitza, 2017; Hambrick & Quigley, 2014; Blettner et al., 2012). The world is increasingly getting complex, and so are local governments. With multiple dynamic and competing factors coming into play, there is need to put in place effective strategic management with good leadership plan to meet modern management challenges in counties. To compete successfully in this environment, counties continually need to improve their performance by reducing cost, innovating products and processes and improving quality, productivity and speed to market (Rumelt, 2011). Strategic Competitive advantage is what keeps great organizations ahead of their competitors. Rothaermel (2012) pointed out that the organization which has a competitive advantage performs better financially than other competitors in the industry. Some companies may achieve it without a strategic plan but for most players, its vital to plan strategically (Rothmeyer, 2012) so are the counties since they're like organizations. Strategic management activities transform the strategic plan into a system that provides strategic performance feedback to decision making and enables the plan to evolve and grow as requirements. Strategy Execution by competent leaders is basically synonymous with Strategy Management and amounts to the systematic implementation of a strategy (Hambrick et al, 2012).

The strategic leader considers the benefits of achieving the strategy and finds the challenges worthwhile (Morebusiness.com Editors, 2007). There are four approaches that are used by strategic leaders (Whittington, 2002). The first approach is the classical theory where the objective of the leaders is profit making. Rational thinking is used to attain it. If a business is not profitable it is discarded. The second theory, evolutionary theory is different in that it does not focus on rationality alone. Globally the environment in which the business is operating in is a critical factor. A radical kind of thinking and flexibility is required in complex and dynamic environments. By firms operating strategically in the dynamic environment, they ensure continuity of the organization (Ansoff, 1985). Many scholars have argued classical approach is irrelevant since it does not put into consideration the current dynamic environments (Skaik, 2009).

Strategic management ensures work is done. Managers focus on the daily directing and controlling activities. It is the authority and role given to them by the organization. The strategic managerial skills are a great asset though deficient in the current fast-paced changing environment globally (Coach4growth Editors, 2010). This is because strategic management is mostly reactive to situations. Non strategic manager globally do nothing to offset most of the future risk (CMOE Editors, 2010). They may even resist change instead of adapting to it and seeing the opportunities and competitive advantages therein. Strategic Managers end up doing a lot of fire-fighting and are not proactive. Energy is

spent mostly on resolving issues instead of analyzing the local and global environment. A strategic manager has a vision and a goal but that is hardly enough. Strategic global Leadership is creative, innovative and proactive (Sullivan, 2006). With the changing and highly competitive global business environment, it is paramount for the company to practice strategic leadership. Leaders anticipate troubles and opportunities. They are highly observant and aware of their surroundings and the changes therein. To a strategic leader flexibility means staying open to opportunities as they arise (Mazur, 2010). They observe the emerging trends and patterns and adjust to the global changing business climate.

Regionally strategic leadership is very important element in the running of an organization since its assist to meet the goals and objectives set by an organization hence helps in smooth running of the organization in general. Similarly, for an organization to survive in the market for a long time competitively it must embrace strategic leadership in totality. In Uganda, experts have historically established that good strategic leadership produces good management, performance, accountability of public money, public behavior and better outcomes of public services (Sullivan & Skelcher, 2017). Good strategic leaders in the county government should guide their county government in the proper direction. This means that their values, vision and purpose are for the good of the county government and its stakeholders. Ethical leaders epitomize the values, vision, and purpose of the organization and of the constituents, within an understanding of ethical ideals (Lewis, 2012). Muasya (2017) the role of strategic leadership in effective strategy implementation a case study of UNICEF Somalia which illustrates very well good relationship between leadership strategies and proves that its very crucial in performance of an organization.

Strategic Leadership is conceived as a process where one or more persons influence a group of persons to move in a certain direction. Messick & Krammer (2014) argued that the degree to which the individual exhibits leadership traits depends not only on his characteristics and personal abilities, but also on the characteristics of the situation and environment in which he finds himself. According to Pearce and Robinson (2014), strategic leadership is about coping with change; and more changes always demand more leadership. Hitt, Ireland and Hoskisson (2014) define strategic leadership as the leader's ability to anticipate, envision, and maintain flexibility to empower others to create strategic change as necessary; it involves managing through others. Capon (2016) defines strategic leadership as the ability to influence a group towards the achievement of goals. He further states that good leadership has strategic vision and is persuasive at implementing strategy to achieve tangible results. Lynch (2015) is of the view that strategic leadership typically involves communicating with and listening to those inside the organization with the aim of spreading knowledge, creating and innovating new areas and solutions to problems. It is the process of allocating resources to support the chosen strategies.

The African strategic leadership process includes the various management activities that are necessary to put strategy in motion, institutes strategic controls that monitor progress, and ultimately achieve organizational goals (Barnat, 2014). Thompson, Strickland and Gamble (2010) emphasizes that there can be no doubt that effective organizational leadership and the consistency of a strong organizational culture are two central ingredients in enabling successful execution of a firm's strategies and objectives. Weak leadership can wreck the soundest strategy; forceful execution of even a poor plan can often bring victory. Strategy implementation may be said to consist of securing resources, organizing these resources and directing the use of these resources within and outside the organization (Mintzberg, 1994). Strategy implementation is only successful when it is backed by effective leadership. House & Mitchell (2014) mentions that effective leaders clearly specify the task, reduce road blocks to task achievement, and increase opportunities for task related satisfaction and improve performance. This clearly shows that strategic leadership is linked to organization performance.

Locally ,strategic leadership is more significant as in the case of Masungu, et al., (2015) who established the effect of strategic leadership on the performance of devolved government system in Kakamega County, Kenya whereby they noted that performance of devolved systems was dependent to the strategic leadership .Kitonga, et al.,(2016) who found that leadership strategies are very important in the overall success of the entire organization in general. Similarly Abba (2016) assessed the influence of strategic leadership in strategy implementation in commercial banks whereby he found out that for organizations to meet their long term strategic growth they must put up strategic leadership well in place always , Mutia (2015) did a study on strategic leadership and its influence on church growth in Kenya where he found out that organization should place an emphasis on training and development to upgrade the existing skill and knowledge base of the employees for effective performance

In the year 2010, Kenya ushered in a highly ambitious form of government that sought to change the relationship between the government and citizens when the constitution was promulgated (COK 2010). The constitution saw shifting of government from centralized to decentralized, and from “top-down” to “bottom up”. Its emphasis is on strengthening public participation. It is a core element in Kenya’s strategy to accelerate growth and address long-standing inequalities in economic opportunities, investment, and service delivery in different parts of the country. Forty-seven county governments were created under Chapter eleven of Constitution of Kenya. The functions of county governments in Kenya came into existence in 2013 when the country elected its leaders under the new dispensation of devolution. The county governments are in charge of health care, pre-primary education and maintenance of local roads. They also, collect revenue in their areas of jurisdiction such as taxes on property and entertainment (Kimenyi, 2013). According to the constitution, only 15% of the government revenue is allocated to the counties whereas 85% remains in the central government, COK 2010. Mwangi (2013) states that each county gets its share (i.e. out of the 15%) based on an horizontal formula that was set by the Commission of Revenue Allocation (CRA) based on the weightings: population 45%, poverty index 20%, land area 8%, basic equal share 25%, fiscal responsibility 2%. Because each county is autonomous in determining on how to spend its financial resources in meeting its development agenda, there is need to assess their ability in managing resources for the purposes of effective service delivery to the people (GOK, 2013). The constitution also gives a provision for those counties that mobilize and manage their resources to be rewarded by receiving a higher share of the central government revenue. In Kenya, since independence the Government has been implementing local government reform programmes with the view of enhanced service delivery thus good performance but this effort have met several challenges. This is the baseline why this study seeks to investigate the effect of strategic leadership on the performance of county governments.

The county government of Uasin Gishu is managed from the county head office at the former Municipal hall, its enjoys good old structures that have been in existence for a very long time and barely are new structures within the county head offices, which makes the county maintain its original heritage. The county government strategies are important such that they should be aligned with good competent leadership so as to achieve the county government objectives of service delivery to its locals according to local government devolution directions. The research done by Kipkorir (2013) on the factors influencing implementation of strategic plans in local authorities in Migori County suggested that organizational culture, structure, strategic leadership and financial resources affected the implementation of the strategic plan. The study conducted by Obiga (2014) focused on the challenges faced during the formulation and implementation of strategy within the County Government of Nairobi. Another study closely related to this was on the strategic planning and implementation practices in Kisii County conducted by Opano (2013) which suggested that poverty line and high mortality rate were some of the challenges faced by the County Government in implementing the strategic plans.

Effective leadership Strategy execution is a process by which strategies are put into concrete action through improvement of programs, budgets, and actions by competent strategic managers. The process is often referred to as operational planning and usually comprise the allocation of day-to-day decisions in resource allocations. Facts from the extant literature reveals that competitive advantages rooted in organizational internal competencies can be more safer in creating benefits for institutions, in contrast to its external opportunities (Arasa & K`obonyo, 2012). One of the organizational internal competitive superiorities is leadership style (Safarzadeh et al. 2015). Strategic leadership was hypothesized to have a positive impact on organizational innovativeness (Safarzadeh et al. 2015). Also, strategic leaders have been repetitively recognized for their decisive role in recognizing opportunities and taking positive decisions that will have impact on innovation process (Safarzadeh et al. 2015). More so, strategic leadership and organizational innovativeness are considered to be fundamentals for achieving and maintaining strategic competitiveness in the 21st century. For the successful implementation of strategies, the challenge of leadership is to be strong but not rude, to be good but not weak, to be humble but not shy, to be proud but not arrogant, to have humor but without foolishness. Strategy can also be explained as choosing one process or several processes to achieve the main long-term goals of the organization. It also includes courses of action and the allocation of resources needed to achieve the desired objectives. (Elkhdr, 2019).

Strategy can be explained as choosing one process or several processes to achieve the main long-term goals of the organization. It also includes courses of action and the allocation of resources needed to achieve the desired objectives. (Elkhdr, 2019). Various scholars have argued that methodological and statistical limitations, unavailability of relevant control variables and contexts have systematically undermined the effect of strategic leadership on performance (Fitza,

2017). Boal & Hooijberg (2001) observe that studies on strategic leadership are limited since many have used demographic variables as substitutes for moderating or mediating variables. Crossan et al., (2008) argue that many studies have excluded critical organizational and environmental variables that might moderate or mediate such a relationship. Additionally, empirical literature has solely examined the impact of strategic leadership at the micro levels without integrating both the micro and macro perspectives of leadership (Bornardi et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2014).

The core purpose of strategic leadership theory and research is to understand how much influence top executives have over performance (Singh et al. 2016). As noted above the various researches done by scholars were done on already early established organizations which the researchers had previous knowledge and materials to refer to whereas my research is on county governments which are new institutions in Kenya with little or no previous history or materials in Kenya. Despite application of strategic leadership in county government there have been challenges of competency, qualifications, motivation, involvement, bureaucracies, relatable values, reception, clarity, service delivery, and efficiency in county government of Uasin Gishu. Therefore the study seeks to determine the effects of work environment on performance of county government in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya.

2. EFFECT OF WORK ENVIRONMENT ON PERFORMANCE IN COUNTY GOVERNMENT OF UASIN GISHU, KENYA

Workplace environment is the sum of the interrelationships that exists within the employees and the environment in which they work (Kohun, 2002). According to Heath (2006), this environment involves the physical location as well as the immediate surroundings, behavioral procedures, policies, rules, culture, resources, working relationships, work location, all of which influence the ways employees perform their work. The quality of the workplace environment impacts on employees' performance and subsequently influences the organization competitiveness. An effective workplace environment management entails making work environment attractive, comfortable, satisfactory and motivating to employees so as to give employees a sense of pride and purpose in what they do (Humphries, 2005). Employees will and are always contented when they feel their immediate environment; both physical sensations and emotional states are in tandem with their obligations (Farh, 2012) and how well employees connect with their organization's immediate workplace environment, influences to a great extent their error rate levels, efficiency and innovativeness, collaboration with other employees, absenteeism and, ultimately their retention (Leblebici, 2012) The type of workplace environment in which employees operate determines whether or not such organizations' will prosper (Chandrasekhar, 2011). Physical workplace environment contextualizes the office layout and design while psychosocial factors include working condition, role congruity and social support from supervisors. Policies encompass employment conditions of employees derived from industrial instruments and agreements negotiated with employees and unions, along with our

Working environment plays an important role towards the employees' performance. Working environment is argued to impact immensely on employees' performance either towards negative or the positive outcomes (Chandrasekar 2011). In the world, there are international organizations who debate the rights of employee. Most people spend fifty percent of their lives within indoor environments, which greatly influence their mental status, actions, abilities and performance (Dorgan, 2014). Better outcomes and increased productivity is assumed to be the result of better workplace environment. Better physical environment of office will boost the employees and ultimately improve their productivity. Various literature pertain to the study of multiple offices and office buildings indicated that the factors such as dissatisfaction, cluttered workplaces and the physical environment are playing a major role in the loss of employees' productivity (Croome, 2017). The factors of work environment had changed due to the changes in several factors such as the social environment, information technology and the flexible ways of organizing work processes (Hasun & Makhbul, 2015). When employees' are physically and emotionally fit will have the desire to work and their performance outcomes shall be increased.

In today's competitive business environment, organizations can no longer afford to waste the potential of their workforce. There are key factors in the employee's workplace environment that impact greatly on their level of motivation and performance. The workplace environment that is set in place impacts employee morale, productivity and engagement - both positively and negatively. It is not just coincidence that new programs addressing lifestyle changes, work/life balance, health and fitness - previously not considered key benefits - are now primary considerations of potential employees, and common practices among the most admired companies. In an effort to motivate workers, firms have

implemented a number of practices such as performance based pay, employment security agreements, practices to help balance work and family, as well as various forms of information sharing. In addition to motivation, workers need the skills and ability to do their job effectively. And for many firms, training the worker has become a necessary input into the production process.

Employee performance is the combined result of effort, ability, and perception of tasks (Platt, 2010). Employees' performance is imperative for organizational outcomes and success. Many factors influence employee performance; and workplace environment factors stands out as the key determinants of performance. It is the key multi character factor intended to attain outcomes and has a major connection with planned objectives of the organization (Sabir et al. 2012). Favourable workplace environment guarantees the wellbeing of employees as well as enables them to exert themselves to their roles with all energy that may translate to higher performance (Taiwo, 2010). To survive and grow, institutions have to embrace strategies of keeping the quality of the workplace high as a competitive strategy. Since employees are the key resource and greatest expense of any institution, the long-term benefits of a properly designed and user-friendly workplace environment should be factored into any initial cost considerations (Smith, 2011) Thus work environment is key in performance of an organization.

The concept of organizational performance is connected to the ideas of effectiveness and efficiency (Kaplan & Norton, 2016). A business organization must produce the right things and it must produce them using the fewest possible inputs if it is to have a strong organizational performance. Businesses typically try to perform well in a number of areas. First, they try to perform well financially. That is, they need to realize a good return on their investment. They need to add as much value as possible in their production process. Second, they try to perform well in terms of the market or non-financial performance. What this means is that they must appropriately manage the determinants that lead to excellent performance. The performance determinants comprise of continuous learning and growth, and efficient internal processes.

Didier Noyé (2002) believes that the performance consists in achieving the goals that were given to you in convergence of enterprise orientations. In his opinion, performance is not a mere finding of an outcome, but rather it is the result of a comparison between the outcome and the objective. Unlike other authors, Didier Noyé considers that this concept is actually a comparison of the outcome and the objective. The author's definition is far from clear, as both outcomes and objectives vary, most often, from one field of activity to another. Author Michel Lebas (1995) characterizes the performance as future-oriented, designed to reflect particularities of each organization / individual and is based on a causal model linking components and products. He defines a "successful" business as one that will achieve the goals set by the management coalition, not necessarily one that achieved them. Thus, performance is dependent as much of capability and future. Unlike other authors, Michel Lebas noted the difference between "a performance", "performance" and "being performant". "A performance" is subject generally to a measured result, higher than that provided for or arising from the previous results. "A performance" thus indicates always a positive connotation. "Performance" can be both positive and negative and relates to past results.

For Whooley (1996), performance is not an objective reality, waiting somewhere to be measured and assessed, but a socially constructed reality that exists in people's minds, if it exists somewhere. According to the author, performance may include: components, products, consequences, impact and can also be linked to economy, efficiency, effectiveness, cost effectiveness or equity. Both Lebas (1995) and Whooley (1996) consider performance as subjective and interpretative, not least, being related to the cost lines, which emphasizes the ambiguous nature of the concept. Neely (2002) believes that performance should consider quantifying the efficiency and effectiveness of actions. This quantification can be expressed both qualitatively and quantitatively. According to the definition of Neely and other authors, performance is closely related to efficiency and effectiveness. Kane (1996) argues that the performance is "something that a person leaves behind and which exists outside the said purpose". According to Kane, performance is defined at the level of each individual within the organization or at organization level. It is perceived as an understanding of the achieved results. The author emphasizes the particular nature of the definition and the impossibility of outlining a general definition. Therefore, we can speak of an accuracy of the definition at particular level and an ambiguity of it at general level.

Traditionally most of the managerial performance measures have been based on financial measures of performance (Mishra and Mohanty, 2014). Also, it is mentioned that these measures include return on assets (ROA), return on equity, and return on sales (Mishra and Mohanty, 2014). In order to define the firm's performance it is important to mention that "financial indicators reflect the fulfillment of a multinational enterprises' (MNE's) economic goals in financial terms (Richter et al., 2017). Also, "market-based financial indicators take the investor's view (e.g. cumulative abnormal returns, market-to-book ratio, excess value) and concentrate on or involve risk considerations (Richter et al., 2017). According to Richter et al. (2017) all these indicators form "the narrowest conception of business performance and the border conceptualization of performance is operational performance". In this context it is necessary to mention the following aspects: -"operational indicators focus on those key determinants of success that might lead to financial performance (Richter et al., 2017); -effectiveness measures include reputation, survival, achievement of goals, performance in relation to competitors, etc. (Richter et al., 2017); -operational effectiveness, organizational effectiveness and financial performance (indicators) are interrelated" (Richter et al., 2017); -organizational effectiveness performance is supposed to be reflected in better financial performance in the medium or long term, because performance improvement is at the heart of strategic management and organization theory" (Venkatraman and Ramanujam 1986; Ginsberg and Venkatraman, 1985; in Richter et al., 2017); -financial performance influences organizations and operational and organizational performance (Richter et al., 2017).

Finally they strategic leader who are vital managers must strive to achieve organizational effectiveness by, quality service delivery, customer satisfaction and creation of a conducive environment for service delivery. In addition, they need to perform well in terms of creating customer loyalty and building trust. According to (Lehner, 2014) Non-financial performance is by assessing the activities that an organization sees as important to the achievement of its strategic objectives. Typical non financial measures include; measures that relate to customer relationships, employees, operations, quality, cycle-time, and the organization's supply chain or its pipeline.

3. METHOD

A descriptive survey research design was employed with a target population of 95 respondents consisting of the county executive committee members, county chief officers, county directors, chief principals, and principals. The data collection instrument was questionnaires both closed and open ended. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the research instrument. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. Data collected using questionnaires was entered and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software. In addition, inferential statistics that include Analysis of variance, Pearson correlation and multiple regression analysis was used establishing the nature and extent of relationship between variables. To ascertain the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable, a regression model was used.

4. DISCUSSION

Workplace environment is the sum of the interrelationships that exists within the employees and the environment in which they work (Kohun, 2002). According to Heath (2006), this environment involves the physical location as well as the immediate surroundings, behavioral procedures, policies, rules, culture, resources, working relationships, work location, all of which influence the ways employees perform their work. Employees will and are always contented when they feel their immediate environment; both physical sensations and emotional states are in tandem with their obligations (Farh, 2012) and how well employees connect with their organization's immediate workplace environment, influences to a great extent their error rate levels, efficiency and innovativeness, collaboration with other employees, absenteeism and, ultimately their retention (Leblebici, 2012) The type of workplace environment in which employees operate determines whether or not such organizations" will prosper (Chandrasekhar, 2011). The study sought to determine the effects of work environment on performance of county government in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya. The findings are presented in a five point Likerts scale where SA=strongly agree, A=agree, N=neutral, D=disagree, SD=strongly disagree and T=total.

Results from table 1 below on whether having good working practices facilitates the performance of county government revealed that 43.0 percent of the respondents strongly agreed, 35.0 percent of them agreed, 1.0 percent of the respondents were neutral, 16.0 percent disagreed while 4.0 percent of them strongly disagreed. These findings implied that having good working practices facilitates the performance of county government.

Following closely on the issue of attitude was the question of whether relatable values in a working environment facilitates a great performance of county government. The distribution of the responses indicated that 33.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 31.0 percent of them agreed, 2.0 percent of them were neutral, 18.0 percent of them disagreed while 16.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that relatable values in a working environment facilitates a great performance of county government.

The respondents were also asked whether a supportive atmosphere as an effective working environment facilitates County government performance. The distribution of the responses indicated that 35.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 32.0 percent of them agreed, none of them were neutral, 18.0 percent of them disagreed while 16.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that a supportive atmosphere as an effective working environment facilitates County government performance.

The respondents were further asked whether a great working environment is contributed much more by the style of leadership in county government. The distribution of the responses indicated that 37.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 28.0 percent of them agreed, 5.0 percent of them were neutral while 20.0 percent and 10.0 percent of them disagreed strongly and disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that a great working environment is contributed much more by the style of leadership in county government.

Table 1: Effect of work environment on performance of county government in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD
Having good working practices facilitates the performance of county government	43.0	35.0	1.0	16.0	4.0
Relatable values in a working environment facilitates a great performance of county government	33.0	31.0	2.0	18.0	16.0
A supportive atmosphere as an effective working environment facilitates County government performance	35.0	32.0	0.0	18.0	16.0
A great working environment is contributed much more by the style of leadership in county government	37.0	28.0	5.0	20.0	10.0

4.1 Inferential Statistics

4.1.1 Pearson Correlation

The study sought to establish the strength of the relationship between independent and dependent variables of the study. Pearson correlation coefficient was computed at 95 percent confidence interval (error margin of 0.05). Table 2 illustrates the findings of the study.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

	Performance of Uasin Gishu County Government
Working environment	Pearson Correlation .899**
	Sig. (2-tailed) .000
	N 85

Results as shown on Table 2 above, the p-value for working environment was found to be 0.000 which is less than the significant level of 0.05, ($p < 0.05$). The result indicated that Pearson Correlation coefficient (r-value) of 0.899, which represented a strong, positive relationship between working environment on performance of Uasin Gishu county government.

4.1.2 Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple linear regressions were computed at 95 percent confidence interval (0.05 margin error) to show the multiple linear relationship between the independent and dependent variables of the study.

4.1.2.1 Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Table 3 shows that the coefficient of correlation (R) is positive 0.476. This means that there is a positive correlation between the effects of leadership strategies on performance of Uasin Gishu county government, Kenya. The coefficient of determination (R Square) indicates that 23.6% of performance of Uasin Gishu county government, Kenya is influenced by leadership strategies. The adjusted R² however, indicates that 19.5% of leadership strategies is influenced by the performance of Uasin Gishu county government, Kenya leaving 80.5% to be influenced by other factors that were not captured in this study.

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.476 ^a	.236	.195	.90429350

a. **Predictors:** (Constant), Working Environment

4.1.2.2 Analysis of Variance

Table 4 shows the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The p-value is 0.000 which is < 0.05 indicates that the model is statistically significant in predicting leadership strategies affect performance of Uasin Gishu county government. The results also indicate that the independent variables are predictors of the dependent variable. The ANOVA results indicate that the independent variables significantly (F=7.841, P=0.000) explain the variance of performance of Uasin Gishu county government.

Table 4 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	246.214	4	4.712	7.841	.000 ^b
	Residual	77.050	80	.832		
	Total	313.264	85			

A. Dependent Variable: Performance of Uasin Gishu County Government

B. Predictors: (Constant), Working Environment

4.1.2.3 Regression Coefficients

From the Coefficients table (Table 4.5) the regression model can be derived as follows:

$$= 0.079 + 0.598X_4$$

The results in table 5 indicate that all the independent variables have a significant positive effect on performance of Uasin Gishu county government. The working environment with a coefficient of 0.598 (p-value = 0.000) influences performance of Uasin Gishu county government. According to this model when all the independent variable values are zero; performance of Uasin Gishu county government of will have a score of 0.079.

Table 5: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.079	.091		.019	.000
	Working environment	.598	.105	.393	3.571	.000

A. Dependent Variable: Performance of Uasin Gishu County Government

4.1.3 Hypothesis Testing

H₀: Working environment does not have a significant effect on performance of Uasin Gishu county government.

From Table 5 above, working environment ($\beta = .598$) was found to be positively related performance of Uasin Gishu county government. From t-test analysis, the t -value was found to be 3.571 and the p -value 0.000. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $p < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that working environment affect performance of Uasin Gishu county government.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion basing on the findings, the study concluded that working environment has a significant effect on performance of Uasin Gishu county government. The study recommended that the management of the county government of Uasin Gishu should provide their employees a fair and conducive working condition to enable high performance. Due to an ever changing environment, the county government of Uasin Gishu should embrace regular trainings to enhance high and required competencies that facilitates good county government performance. The management of the county government of Uasin Gishu should establish a good relationship with their stakeholders through provision of good reception to enhance customer satisfaction.

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